

Progress report on the Rust/Node.js Web Audio API implementation

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ABSTRACT

At the Web Audio Conference 2022[2] we presented a novel implementation of the Web Audio API that can be used outside of the web browser. With this library, one can build audio graphs with Node.js or Rust, for e.g. command line interfaces or native applications, using the well documented and familiar Web Audio API. Since then we have made progress on feature completeness, performance and correctness. These objectives have been driven by results from independent web audio benchmark suites and the web-platform-tests project. This talk provides a brief overview of the relevant developments and future plans with the project.

1 Introduction

Our implementation decouples the Web Audio API from the web (and web browsers), potentially opening new application areas and helping to widen its community of users. The project consists of a low-level implementation¹ of the API written in the Rust language, and another codebase² providing bindings of this library to the Node.js platform.

Despite the name, the Web Audio API is rather isolated from other Web standards which makes it relatively simple to decouple it from the browser. However, it interfaces with a few other components such as the Media Devices API, Media Streams API, HTMLMediaElement, EventTarget and MessagePort. For these we have introduced lightweight shims in Rust, trying to stick as close as possible to their official specification and providing the minimally required functionality.

We have chosen to implement the audio backbone in the Rust programming language. Rust is a low-level, memory-efficient language such as C or C++ suitable for real-time audio engines with predictive timing and high performance. Compared to C and C++, the Rust compiler is able to reason about thread safety and data races. This gives us confidence our application is actually memory safe, but on the other hand it makes implementing certain patterns, such as graph data structures, more cumbersome. It also enables

¹<https://github.com/orottier/web-audio-api-rs>

²<https://github.com/ircam-ismm/node-web-audio-api>

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Web Audio Conference WAC-2024, March 15–17, 2024, West Lafayette, IN, USA.

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bindings to the Node.js platform via the Node-API application binary interface.

According to the GitHub dependency graph our Rust implementation is used in a few gaming projects, an emulator, and a command line digital signal processor. The Node.js library is used likewise for CLI programs, and is heavily used in experimental distributed music systems composed of low-powered devices (such as the Raspberry Pi) developed at Ircam.

2 Recent developments

A lot of effort was put into the performance of the audio library. In our 2023 paper[1] we presented speedups of 2-5 times compared to the 2022 implementation. This brings us closer to the performance of web browser implementations as measured by two independent performance benchmark suites^{3 4}. It has also uncovered areas that need further improvements such as AudioParam handling, convolution and large scale audio graphs. Further profiling and development of these components should help identify and mitigate these bottlenecks, alongside more generic improvements such as SIMD processing and fast math operations.

Our implementation is now being tested with the web-platform-tests suite⁵. This suite, maintained by the browser vendors, contains over 8000 assertions regarding the Web Audio API that can be run cross-browser. With a third-party tool⁶, these javascript tests can be run in Node.js, hence also for our bindings. So far, this has brought up many erroneous edge cases and some missing functionality in our software that we are currently fixing. For example, in the current state, the AudioParam test suite seems to indicate some slight numerical discrepancies to be investigated. A comprehensive quantitative analysis is complicated by the fact that some tests require functionality that is specific to the browser, such as the behavior of the API in relation to DOM components or windows/frames.

3 Future plans

Our short term goals are threefold. One is to continue to investigate and improve upon the web platform tests results. Obviously we are aiming for a 100% score in all tests that do not require browser-specific components. Then we need

³<https://github.com/padenot/webaudio-benchmark>

⁴<https://github.com/spotify/web-audio-bench/>

⁵<https://github.com/web-platform-tests/wpt>

⁶<https://github.com/domenic/wpt-runner>

to address a few missing features of the Rust implementation such as multi channel convolution and stereo-to-stereo HRTF panning. The final short term goal is to be able to run the `AudioWorkletNode` natively in `Node.js`.

The long term planning consists of more performance work and Python bindings to the library. It could also prove useful to also bring other web APIs in scope, such as the Web MIDI API and the Web Codecs API. Other web media APIs such as WebRTC already have excellent standalone implementations. We could provide a module to connect our Web Audio implementation to these libraries.

Obviously, we aim to track the new developments of the Web Audio specification.

4 Conclusion

All in all, we believe both our libraries are suitable for production grade audio applications and deliver immediate value to developers aiming to deploy their Web Audio expertise outside of web browsers.

5 References

- [1] B. Matuszewski and O. Rottier. The Web Audio API as a Standardized Interface Beyond Web Browsers. *Journal of the Audio Engineering Society* <http://www.aes.org/e-lib/browse.cfm?elib=22344>, 71(11):790–801, November 2023.
- [2] O. Rottier and B. Matuszewski. A Rust Implementation of the Web Audio API. In *Web Audio Conference 2022 (WAC 2022) Cannes, France*, page <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6767674>, July 2022.

CCS Concepts

•**Applied computing** → **Sound and music computing**;
•**Software and its engineering** → *Software libraries and repositories*; •**Information systems** → World Wide Web;

Keywords

Web Audio API, Rust, `Node.js`